

Advances in Hyaluronic-Acid-Based (Nano)Devices for Cancer Therapy

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Cancer is the main cause of fatality all over the world with a considerable growth rate. Many biologically active nanoplatforms are exploited for tumor treatment. Of nanodevices, hyaluronic acid (HA)-based systems have shown to be promising candidates for cancer therapy due to their high biocompatibility and cell internalization. Herein, surface functionalization of different nanoparticles (NPs), e.g., organic- and inorganic-based NPs, is highlighted. Subsequently, HA-based nanostructures and their applications in cancer therapy are presented.

linked by β -1-3 and β -1-4 glycosidic bonds, naturally present in the extracellular matrix (ECM) of all mammalian cells.^[4,5] HA is ubiquitous in soft connective tissues of all vertebrate adults, in which it plays both a mechanical and a cellular instructive role. Biological functions concerning HA consist of tissue hydration, water retention and homeostasis in the matrix, lubrication, cell migration, neutrophil adhesion, cell interaction and division, and it is involved in the morphogenesis and repair

1. Introduction

Cancer is the second most common cause of death in the world, with an increasing growth rate, with 300 000 new cases annually diagnosed, as reported by the World Health Organization.^[1] Over the years more and more researchers have focused on the development of novel nanoplatforms or on the amelioration of the current nanosystems for efficacious treatment of cancer as one of the most significant objectives in the biomedical sector.^[2] A large number of different nanomaterials and preparative methods were proposed for the production of devices able to simultaneously protect therapeutic molecules in the physiological environment and to deliver them to the diseased area.^[3] In light of this, hyaluronic acid (HA)-based systems have attracted much attention in cancer therapy. HA is a linear, anionic, nonsulfated polysaccharide, belonging to the class of glycosaminoglycans. HA is composed of repeating disaccharide units of D-glucuronic acid and N-acetyl-D-glucosamine

of wounds. Its intracellular biological functions, although not yet fully characterized, has been assumed to be related to the control of cell proliferation and inflammation. Currently, it is safety used in multiple medical field, including treatments for the tissue augmentations, dry eye, wound and osteoarthritis, and in numerous surgical and drug delivery applications due to its intrinsic biocompatibility, nontoxicity, biodegradability, and nonimmunogenicity.^[6-8] These advantages made it a great candidate to use as raw material for the production of carriers in targeted-specific drug release. It is also used to functionalize other materials to enhance their biocompatibility as well as the targeting efficiency, since it interacts with receptors (e.g., CD44) overexpressed in tumor cells.^[9] Herein, the functionalization of both organic and inorganic nanostructures with HA is presented, illustrating HA-based systems including hydrogels, nanoparticles (NPs) and other nanoarchitectures for tumor treatment. Finally, the advances of these HA-based platforms in cancer therapy is highlighted to pave the way for future research in this field.

2. Hyaluronic-Acid-Based Devices

Since the 1990s, Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved nanotechnology devices based products and clinical trials has remarkably increased and about ten years later HA nanodevices have gained a prominent role in the cancer therapy field used to formulate drug delivery systems to improve therapeutic efficacy. HA nanodevices have several important features such as very low immunogenicity, biodegradability, noninflammatory reactions, bioavailability and biocompatibility. These specific features make HA the principal component of multifunctional nanodevices for a wide set of cancer therapies.^[10] In particular, to the best of our knowledge, in 2007 the first example of HA-based nanogels, with a size distribution from 200 to 500 nm, to target-specific intracellular delivery of siRNA was published.^[11] A few years later, other nanodevices for cancer treatment such as hydrogel and particulate systems were developed. HA-based

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Scheme 1. Schematic representations of the functional properties of the HA (nano) devices.

nanodevices are particularly interesting for drug delivery since, in addition to above cited features, their functional properties allow to have a controlled and targeted drug release in response to different triggers that turns out to be attractive in cancer therapy.^[12] According to the physicochemical properties and structures of the devices, they can be categorized in endogenous stimuli-responsive devices, comprising pH, enzyme and redox responsive materials; exogenous stimuli-responsive devices, such as light, temperature, ultrasound and magnetic field responsive materials; multi-stimuli responsive materials; moreover, in particular the HA-based nanodevices resulted to be promising for their active targeting functional properties^[13] (Scheme 1). HA can therefore be a constituent element of the architecture of these nanodevices or an element covering them.

2.1. Hydrogels and Nanogels

HA-based hydrogels were proposed as chemotherapy drug delivery systems, able to target the cancer site and to ensure the controlled local administration, with the aim of overcome the side effects of the systemic administration. Hydrogels are insoluble polymeric hydrophilic networks, able to absorb water until it reaches a wet weight a thousand times higher than the dry one.^[14] These materials can be prepared by crosslinking polymer chains (or supramolecular aggregates) through the formation of chemical bonds (chemical hydrogels) or not covalent interactions (physical hydrogels).^[15,16] Hydrogels are viscoelastic materials containing an high amount of water, that allows them to be loaded not only with drugs, but also with nutrients, cells and/or growth factors,^[17] and regulate their in situ release. These properties make hydrogel highly versatile for biomedical applications, and induced researchers to focus their attention on them for the design of devices for cancer therapy.^[18] HA results partic-

ularly suitable for the production of hydrogels thanks to its reactive groups, that can be modified to prepare different kinds of crosslinkable polymers, able to form chemical and physical hydrogels;^[19] moreover, in literature it is also reported that, due to its negative charge, HA can be crosslinked in presence of cations without any modification.^[20] Besides traditional chemotherapy drugs (doxorubicin, DOX), HA hydrogels were demonstrated to improve the bioavailability of molecules with therapeutic effects, that normally would have a short life in the organism. HA was used in combination with carboxymethylcellulose to produce chemically crosslinked hydrogels with modifiable mechanical properties and release behavior in function of the two polymers concentration and the ratio in order to optimize the delivery of oxaliplatin.^[21] The targeting ability of HA-based hydrogels can be improved by preparing materials designed to respond to external stimuli, and consequently interact selectively with cancer cells, taking advantage of the different environmental conditions of the cancer tissues (e.g., pH) respect to healthy ones.^[22] Since the surgery implantation of hydrogels could reduce the therapeutic benefits of the device, in the last years a common strategy was the preparation of injectable materials, able to be administrated with a syringe, and that exhibit gel properties after injection.^[23] The advantage of this approach is not only to administrate the device without operating the patient, but in some cases to treat sites that would be unreachable for surgery. Injectable hydrogels can be prepared as solutions able to gel following environmental changes, such as temperature or pH variations, light irradiation and enzymatic action.^[24] A thermosensitive hydrogel prepared from a solution of HA, chitosan and β -glycerophosphate was designed for the release of DOX. HA was evaluated for its ability to enhance the poor mechanical properties of the previously studied chitosan/ β -glycerophosphate system, and was observed to promote the temperature-dependent gelation at acid pH, due to hydrogen bonds that carboxyl groups of HA form with protonated amine groups of chitosan;^[25] moreover, different gelation temperature, gelation time and DOX release rate were observed at different contents of HA. Thermosensitive HA/chitosan-based hydrogels were also evaluated for the control of the release of DOX from graphene oxide conjugated with folic acid;^[26] these nanomaterials were prepared to improve the interesting properties of pH-dependent drug release, and selective targeting of MCF-7 cancer cells of graphene oxide-based materials, that generally undergo burst release in physiological conditions in absence of an external protection. In vivo experiments showed a controlled cytotoxicity of hydrogel loaded with graphite nanosystems, that manifested a high in vivo effectiveness against MCF-7 cells.

A pH-responsive HA nanoconjugated material was prepared by bonding covalently the polymer to mesoporous silica NPs, in order to exploit the high loading capacity of NPs, overcoming their common drawback of burst release.^[27] HA-conjugated NPs were loaded with DOX as model drug and were confirmed to be able to perform pH-sensitive gelation in low pH conditions, with prolonged drug release, that is ruled by the simultaneous HA enzymatic degradation. In vitro experiments showed the biocompatibility of hydrogels with healthy cells (293T), and the targeting and killing action against breast cancer cells (SKBR3).

Another type of stimuli-sensitive materials which are attracting more and more scientific attention for cancer treatment is represented by light-responsive materials for phototherapy.

Figure 1. A) Synthetic scheme for the formation of the hydrogel precursor, illustrating the adipic dihydrazide and the photosensitizer grafted onto the HA backbone, and of the dialdehyde substituted thioketal (ROS sensitive crosslinker). B) In vivo injection and gelation of the ROS-sensitive hydrogel, and NIR-triggered controlled release of DOX. Reprinted with permission.^[31] Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

Phototherapy consists in the irradiation (generally with near-infrared laser) of a molecule capable of absorbing light energy and destroying the tumor by catalyzing the synthesis of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (photodynamic therapy, PDT) or by generating heat (photothermal therapy, PTT).^[28] Unfortunately, the application of PDT is restricted by the physicochemical properties of photosensitizers, that often result slightly soluble in water, and their self-destruction under laser irradiation.^[29] Besides, photosensitizers are not able to specifically target tumor tissues, and can be observed also in normal tissues.^[30] To overcome these limitations, a carrier aimed for photosensitizers transport to tumor sites will enhance the clinical application. A treatment that combines chemotherapy and photodynamic therapy by using an HA-based hydrogel was proposed.^[31] Adipic dihydrazide-modified HA was grafted with protoporphyrin IX, a photosensitizer, and crosslinked with dialdehyde substituted thioketal, to form ROS sensitive crosslinkings (Figure 1A). It was demonstrated that the conjugation of HA and the photosensitizer increased the ROS production, and that the rate of degradation of

hydrogel could be controlled through the time of irradiation; this allowed, as verified in this work, to control the release of DOX. The biocompatibility and the double anticancer action of these systems were confirmed through in vitro test on MCF-7, 4T1 cancer cells and NIH-3T3 healthy cells, and in vivo test on 4T1 cells-bearing mice (Figure 1B). A potential device proposed for the breast cancer photo thermal therapy was prepared by introducing indocyanine green in an dopamine-modified HA hydrogel.^[32] The material was obtained through double crosslinking due to sodium selenite, that is able to make basic the environment, in order to promote dopamine polymerization, and react with HA functional groups. Furthermore, sodium selenite is known for its anticancer ability. The tests conducted in vitro and in vivo showed how the indocyanine loaded into the hydrogel have higher energy conversion efficiency and longer time of retention in tissues.

Injectable hydrogels can also be produced as self-healing materials, that are able to recover their form after a strain, through the formation of reversible chemical bonds.^[33] An hydrogel obtained from the reaction of aldehyde-modified HA with amine groups

Figure 2. Scheme of the formation of redox-sensitive HA nanogels for highly efficient loading and breast tumor-targeted delivery of cytochrome c. Reprinted with permission.^[38] Copyright 2016, American Chemical Society.

of carboxyethyl chitosan was verified to perform pH-dependent gelation and release of DOX in HeLa cells.^[34] An aldehyde modified HA was also used with good in vivo results in combination with carboxymethyl chitosan as injectable device for the release of DOX (covalently bond to HA), and gemcitabine (loaded in the hydrogel) to prevent the recurrence of cancer in the post-surgical cavities.^[35]

A further strategy to prepare injectable stimuli responsive materials for cancer therapy is represented by nanosized hydrogels (or nanogels); the great interest in these nanosystems is due to the possibility to combine the properties of hydrogels (high stability and sensitivity to environmental stimuli) with the advantages of NPs, such as high surface area (and consequently high loading capacity). Nanogels are generally obtained by combining nanoprecipitation with specific crosslinking reactions, that in many cases allow to obtain monodisperse systems of nanometric dimensions, able to improve the cell penetration of therapeutic agents. Nanogels with controlled size for the DOX release were prepared by using HA and keratin.^[36] Keratin is a multifunctional cross linker, that can be used with HA to form pH sensitive crosslinking (formation of hydrogen bonds) and reduction sensitive crosslinking (reduction of thiols to form disulfide bridges). The materials obtained showed a pH/reduction sensitivity also in the release rate of DOX, and higher cytotoxicity respect to the drug alone. Many HA-based nanogels were proposed for the delivery of proteins in cancer protein therapy, whose employment in the treatment of numerous disease is considered more advantageous compared to drugs since having intracellular targets, but

with effectiveness that is generally hindered by their extracellular activity.^[37] In the realization of these devices it is essential that the crosslinking reactions are highly selective, so as not to cause denaturation of protein. Nanogels for the delivery of cytochrome C were prepared by using the with L-cystine dimethacrylamide for the crosslinking of HA grafted with *t*-oligo(ethylene) glycol-tetrazole (HA-OEG-Tet).^[38] The reaction is highly selective, does not require catalysts and forms reduction-sensitive bonds for the specific release of the protein in cancer cells environment. Protein-loaded nanogels resulted in higher penetration and cytotoxicity of the protein-loaded nanogels than nanogels and protein alone during in vitro test on MCF-7 tumor cells. In vivo tests confirmed the targeting and cell penetration abilities on MCF-7 tumor-bearing mice (**Figure 2**).

A DOX-loaded HA nanogel for the treatment of Osteosarcoma was obtained by using cisplatin (CDDP).^[39] CDDP is an antitumor drug generally used to repair DNA crosslinking damages, and that in this work was successfully used to crosslink HA, chelating the carboxyl groups of the polymer. The use of CDDP as crosslinker aims to improve the stability of the nanogels and simultaneously overcome multidrug resistance by using antitumor that acts with different pathways. Nanogels were prepared with a green synthetic method in absence of organic solvents and showed high dimensional stability (72.6 nm) and low DOX release rate (38.5%) at physiological pH after 72 h, while in the same time they exhibited swelling (473.3 nm) and high release rate (86%). Experiments on in mouse osteosarcoma K7 cells highlighted the more efficient DOX internalization after 6 h for the

loaded nanogels respect to the drug alone. Furthermore, pharmacokinetic and biodistribution analysis indicated that nanogels were able to increase the plasma concentration of drugs almost 100 times, and to accumulate preferentially in tumor cells. In vitro and in vivo experiments confirmed the anticancer ability of the nanosystems and the synergy between the two chemotherapeutics. A similar HA-based nanogel was evaluated for the treatment of breast cancer.^[40] The anticancer ability of the nanogels was evaluated through experiments on two different xenograft animal models: MCF-7/ADR and MCF-7-xenografted model. The release of the drugs due to the collapse of the nanogel in the acidic conditions of the cell was observed, and the results illustrated how crosslinked nanosystems exhibited higher in vivo stability and greater anticancer activity, due to the synergy between the two drugs, respect to non-crosslinked materials.

2.2. Self-Assembling and Particulate Nanocarriers

In the last decade, self-assembled aggregates of amphiphilic copolymers have gained a prominent role in the drug delivery field.^[41] These aggregates are composed of a hydrophobic core, in which it is possible to introduce lipophilic molecules, and a hydrophilic shell necessary to increase the circulation time of NPs.^[42] Thanks to its intrinsic biodegradability and biocompatibility, HA resulted very attractive for the design of self-assembled systems to use in cancer drug delivery field; the application of HA as hydrophilic shell could extend blood circulation time of amphiphilic block copolymers, mediate tumor cell specific targeting and ameliorate the in vivo safety. However, HA is a highly hydrophilic polymer that cannot self-assemble directly.^[43] For this reason, it is necessary to use HA in combination with hydrophobic and/or amphiphilic polymers by establishment of physical interactions, or to produce HA amphiphilic derivatives by chemical grafting of hydrophobic groups or drugs on its backbone.^[44] In this context, it was demonstrated that systems formed through physical interactions (ionic, hydrophobic), such as NPs prepared with HA/poly(D,L-lactide-co-glycolide)(PLGA), Pluronic F127 (PF127) and chitosan, were able to encapsulate irinotecan (hydrophobic drugs) and doxorubicin and hinder the activity of topoisomerases II and I.^[45] Instead, NPs based on HA-polycaprolactone (PCL) represented an example of material obtained by an HA amphiphilic block copolymer, in which the use of HA derivatives forming crosslinked shell were able to encapsulate doxorubicin and to retard the drug release.^[46]

In the case of poorly water-soluble drugs, this can be physically incorporated or covalently bond to the HA chain.^[47] In particular, self-assembled HA-NPs, with an internal core, composed of hydrophobic polymers or drugs such as irinotecan, doxorubicin, enclosed by a hydrophilic HA shell, have been widely employed as cancer-targeting nanocarriers for the delivery of therapeutic or diagnostic agents, because HA-NPs specifically bind the CD44, the major cell-surface HA receptor overexpressed on cancer cells. In addition to drug delivery, HA-NPs also have found use in positron emission tomography (PET), targeted magnetic resonance (MR) and ultrasound imaging agents for biomedical applications.^[48]

HA shows three main functional groups available for the chemical modification on its backbone such as the carboxyl, amide, hydroxyl groups.^[49] The carboxyl group is known to be

the target site for both enzyme and receptor.^[50] So, although it was reported that the carboxyl modification can prolong the HA-NPs circulation time by preventing enzymatic degradation, it was demonstrated that it decreases the HA NPs targeting.^[51] For this reason, hydroxyl group modification is a preferable solution to achieve better targeting efficacy, as in the case of HA-glycyrrhetic acid succinate conjugates based NPs. In fact, NPs obtained via modifying the hydroxyl groups of HA, and loaded with hydrophobic drugs, have showed higher efficiency in liver targeting compared to carboxyl group modifications.^[52]

The physical-chemical properties of HA NPs, e.g., particle size and stability in the aqueous solutions, in vitro and in vivo behaviors of self-assembled nanostructures may vary depending on the molecular weight of HA and substitution degree (DS) of a hydrophobic group on the HA backbone. Indeed, it is notable that the targeting efficiency of HA NPs to the tumor cells is significantly conditioned by the DS of the hydrophobic molecules on the HA backbone.^[53] The NPs size and the critical aggregation concentrations (CAC) decrease as the DS increases because stronger interactions between molecules in the hydrophobic core are observed. For this reason, the DS should be controlled to avoid the formation of insoluble HA conjugates due to high hydrophobicity.^[54] Based on the molecular weight, HA may form with the hydrophobic molecules in the aqueous solution a wide set of nano-size particles which is favorable for enhanced permeability and retention (EPR) effect.^[55]

In the last decade, great scientific attention was reserved on the design of HA-based NPs for the photothermal therapy (PTT) field for cancer treatment.^[56] This approach exploits the ability of photothermal agents (PTA) to emit a strong fluorescence, which makes them usable as contrast agents for photoacoustic imaging, with excellent diagnostic and positioning effect for PTT. However, PTAs are limited by the high toxicity they have shown in vivo assays.^[57] Self-assembled HA-OM tumor-targeting NPs were developed applying a chemical modification on the amide group, for photothermal ablation in over-expressing CD44 bladder cancer. Briefly, to produce the HA-IR-780 NPs primarily the HA-NHS ester was synthesized by adding NHS and EDC into formamide solution containing HA. Then, IR-780-NH₂, obtained by modification of IR-780 with 4-aminothiophenol, was added to the HA-NHS mixture and subsequently, the hydrophobic IR-780 was grafted on the HA backbone. To obtain HA-IR-780 NPs, amphiphilic HA-IR-780 was added to phosphate buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) and the solution was purified by means of filter membrane. Furthermore, the NPs were intravenously injected in a mouse animal model, and after the treatment with exposure to 808 nm laser (1 W cm⁻²) for 6 min the tumor volume significantly reduced, as it is possible to note in **Figure 3**. So, HA-IR-780 NPs have shown, high tumor selectivity, good bioavailability, high treatment efficacy, and excellent biocompatibility^[58] (**Table 1**).

Another innovative approach of HA NPs for cancer treatment is photodynamic therapy (PDT).^[59,60] HA NPs have been used as the best candidates for the delivery of hydrophobic photosensitizers.^[61] For instance, stable NPs composed of HA and ϵ -polylysine (EPL) were fabricated by functionalizing the E-polylysine with the thiol group to increase the stability of the aggregates and stabilize the initially HA/EPL formed coacervates.^[62] They manifested many desirable properties, such as the resistance to dilution, tunable size and surface charge,

Figure 3. a) Chemical structure of HA-IR-780 conjugates, preparation of HA-IR-780 NPs and its application in orthotopic bladder cancer; b) representative images of mice bearing orthotopic bladder cancer pretreatment and 12 days after treatments. Reprinted with permission.^[58] Copyright 2017, Elsevier.

Figure 4. A) The HA-SH NPs synthesized by the electrostatic interaction between HA-SH and the CaP core. B-a) Accumulation of NPHA-SH/CaP/siRNA at tumor sites b) receptor-mediated uptake of NPs by B16F10 cells, c) redox-triggered destruction of the HA-ss-HA shell and exposure of the CaP core to the acidic endosome or lysosome, d) dissolution of CaP e) endosomal escape, and f) target gene silencing. C) Analysis of bioluminescence images of B16F10-luciferase xenograft tumors bearing mice. D) Semi quantitative analysis of the image (A). E) On day 2 (24 h after the second injection), the tumors were removed from the mice and the luciferase activity in the tumor tissue was measured. Reprinted with permission.^[63] Copyright 2017, American Chemical Society.

and efficient encapsulation of Chlorin e6 (Ce6), a photosensitizer used for PDT, in the fabricated NPs. In vitro test demonstrated the intracellular delivery efficiency of HA/Ce6-NPs compared to the free Ce6. These results suggested that self-assembled NPs of HA are efficient and biocompatible drug delivery carriers for PDT.^[62]

A novel crosslinking strategy for the stabilization of calcium phosphate NPs and stimuli-responsive small interfering RNA (siRNA) release for melanoma tumor therapy was investigated. A thiolated HA (HA-SH) was synthesized to prepare as a smart redox-responsive delivery system. The system was composed of a positively charged core, where siRNA was engulfed by Calcium Phosphate, and by an anionic shell formed by disulfide crosslinked HA (HA-ss-HA). The selective release of siRNA from CAP/HA-ss-HA NPs system into the cytosol was observed, by both a GSH-triggered disassembly and successful endoso-

mal escape. Therefore, the new hybrid delivery system allowed to reach an 80% gene-silencing efficacy in vitro for both luciferase and Bcl2 resulting in dramatic apoptosis of B16F10 cells. Moreover, the new hybrid delivery system equipped with the tumor-targeting component HA on NPs significantly suppressed the growth of B16F10 xenograft tumor in mice (Figure 4). Apparently, the anionic HA-ss-HA-equipped NPs showed no in vitro or in vivo toxicity, in addition to a high transfection efficiency. Thanks to the simultaneous redox-responsivity and tumor-targeting, these smart HA NPs resulted highly promising for exploitation in functionalized siRNA delivery and tumor therapy.^[63]

Another example of the use a calcium salt as crosslinking agent is represented by the mineralization with CaCO₃ of HA NPs, loaded with DOX for the osteosarcoma treatment.^[64] Ca²⁺ and CO³⁻ ions were added to the previously prepared

Table 1. Representative of HA-based nanodevices in cancer therapy.

Nanodevices	Size	Loaded drug	Tumor model in vitro	Tumor animal model in vivo	Remarks	Ref.
HA-IR-780 conjugates for photothermal therapy	171 nm	–	–	CCK-8 in mice bladder cancer cells	The photothermal therapy of HA-IR-780 NPs show high tumor selectivity, high tumor treatment efficacy	[58]
HA functionalized gold nanorods	70.9 nm	DOX	MFC-7 breast cancer	Tumor-bearing Athymic nude mice (BALB/c-nu)	Long blood circulation time and very good tumor-specific accumulation	[89]
HA/PLGA	184 nm	IRIN	MFC-7 breast carcinoma	–	Positive effect of HA on NP internalization	[94]
HA-based drug conjugate	–	PTX	HepG2 and A549 cells, epato and adeno carcinoma	–	Higher cytotoxicity and enhanced apoptosis, increased cellular uptake of the drug	[106]
HA drug conjugates	–	DOX, GEM	Breast cancer cells	Orthotopic 4T1 tumor model	Effectively inhibits the growth	[108]
HA drug conjugates	–	Pt	Lung cancer cells	Wild-type female C57BL/6 mice	Decrease the cell growth both 2D and 3D cultures, 90% reduction of tumor nodule numbers in vivo	[112]
IFN- α -incorporated HA-Tyr hydrogels plus SRF	–	SRF	–	Mouse model for the treatment for metastatic renal cell carcinoma	Effectively inhibited tumor growth in nude mice, and furthermore the drug delivery system prolongs the biological half-life of natural human IFN- α	[121]
HA-based combination vaccine adjuvants	–	–	–	Mice model of lymphoma expressing OVA	Inhibition of tumor proliferation	[122]
HA recoated <i>N,N,N</i> -trimethyl chitosan (TMC) NPs	–	–	CD44-expressing cancer cells	–	Delivering of IL-6- and STAT3-specific small interfering RNAs, blockade of proliferation, colony formation, migration, and angiogenesis in cancer cells	[125]
Chitosan NPs modified with HA loaded with cyanine 3 (Cy3) labeled siRNA	100–200 nm	–	A549 non-small cell lung cancer	Female BALB/c tumor-bearing mice	Successfully carried the Cy3 labeled siRNA into A549 cells via CD44 receptor, inhibiting cell proliferation by the downregulation of gene target BCL2, both in vitro than in vivo	[127]
HA containing lipid NPs coloaded with Pt and SRF	–	Pt and SRF	–	BALB/cA nude gastric tumor-bearing mice	Enhanced the antitumor effect of drugs and reduced the systemic toxicity effects	[130]
Lys-Leu-Val-Phe-Phe (KLVFF) peptide motifs targeted by HA functionalized liposomes	113 nm	–	4T1 cells breast cancer	4T1 breast cancer mice model	Prevent the activation of intra-tumoral platelet, which suppress tumor progression and the spontaneous lung metastasis	[132]

Abbreviations: DOX: doxorubicin; miR-21: microRNA-21; IRIN: irinotecan; PTX: paclitaxel; GEM: gemcitabine; Pt: cisplatin; SRF: sorafenib.

complex HA-DOX, resulting by electrostatic interaction, to obtain crosslinked NPs with higher stability and pH-dependent structure. In vitro experiments showed the biocompatibility of the nanosystems, and the higher release rate in acidic conditions (89.7%, pH 5.5) than physiological conditions (25.7%, pH 7.4)

after 72 h. In vivo results on the K7 osteosarcoma allografted mouse model illustrated efficient accumulation in the tumor, and higher anticancer activity compared to free DOX and HA-DOX.

Concerning the NPs fabricated by means of chemical modifications on the HA backbone, both biodegradable synthetic and

natural polymers can be used, such as poly(lactide-co-glycolide) (PLGA), polylactic acid (PLA), polycaprolactone (PCL), and poly (butyl cyanoacrylate) (PBCA).

For example, HAssLG diblock copolymer have been designed for application in the sequential targeting of NPs by CD44 receptor-mediated drug delivery. Primarily, poly(DL-lactide-co-glycolide) (PLGA was linked to the HA) through the formation of a disulfide linkage, and then a diblock copolymer (HAssLG) was synthesized. DOX was loaded into HAssLG NPs by dialysis procedure. The addition of GSH to the system showed how the DOX release in a reducing environment the degradation of disulfide bonds resulted in an increased DOX release. In vitro study showed DOX-loaded HAssLG NPs were endocytosed by CD44 receptor-mediated pathway. In vivo NIRF imaging studies also demonstrated that HAssLG NPs were delivered to tumor tissues through a targeting mechanism.^[65]

NPs obtained from the self-assembling of HA/PLA amphiphilic copolymer, and containing peptide-iRGD, were demonstrated to counter the tumor growth and lung metastasis in 4T1 breast cancer xenograft bearing mice. HA/PLA was synthesized by an end to end coupling strategy, in which HA was amino-functionalized by a terminal reductive amination reaction and the carboxyl of PLA was activated by *N*-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS). The cellular uptake of HA/PLA NPs on high CD44-expressing 4T1 cells was markedly higher than the endocytosis on low CD44-expressing L929 fibroblast cells. In vivo test showed HA/PLA NPs prolong the permanence time of DOX in the blood. The HA/PLA NPs combined with iRGD increased both the drug distribution and penetration in tumors, improving in the anti-tumor efficacy, contributing effectively to the inhibition of lung metastases in breast cancer. For this reason, the administration of iRGD embodied in HA/PLA self-assembling aggregates resulted an effective strategy for metastatic breast cancer therapy.^[66]

HA/polycaprolactone (PCL) block copolymer, obtained by crosslinking HA through bio-reducible disulfide bond has been synthesized, and its tumor targeting and drug delivery abilities have been evaluated. The block copolymer was synthesized by means of azide-alkyne cycloaddition, that consisted in the introduction of an alkyne group at the reducing end of HA, that then reacted with PCL-N3. The release of DOX from the HA NPs (DOX-HA-ss-NPs) was observed slow at pH 7.4, in the meanwhile the release rate was significantly improved in a solution containing GSH, the reducing agent of the disulfide bridge present in the cytoplasm. In vitro experiments demonstrated that these NPs are rapidly absorbed by SCC7 cancer cells by means of their interaction with CD44 receptors. The crosslinked NPs significantly minimized the initial drug release. Even in vivo studies showed that the crosslinked NPs in both rise targeting and therapeutic efficacy of the tumor cells compared to non-crosslinked NPs and improved antitumor activity in tumor-bearing mice.^[46]

New nanoformulation composed of HA-polypolybutyl cyanoacrylate (PBCA) and alpha-tocopheryl polyethylene glycol succinate (PGS) with tumor targeting ability for the delivery of morin hydrate (MH) has been developed. HA-PBCA was synthesized by radical reaction at acidic pH, and then MH-HA-PBCA NPs and MH-HAPBCA-PGS NPs were prepared by a probe-type ultrasonic and dialysis method. The cellular uptake studies showed that MH-HAPBCA-PGS NP resulted in higher cellular uptake than that of MH-HA-PBCA NPs, in

A549 cells. In vivo test showed a higher antitumor efficacy of MH-HA-PBCA-PGS NP and induced more tumor cell apoptosis than MH-HA-PBCA NPs, after the intravenous administration to tumor-bearing mice. These results demonstrated the new mixed NPs formulation is a potential vehicle for the targeted delivery of lipophilic anticancer drugs.^[67]

HA and chondroitin sulfate (CD) modified PLGA-PEG copolymers were synthesized and loaded with 1,2-Dioleoyl-3-trimethylammonium-propane, DOTAP/pDNA, (DOT/PD) to produce CD44 receptor targeting NPs for gene delivery. Both types of NPs showed pH-dependent release and exhibited higher release rate at low pH values (4.0) compared to pH physiological pH (7.4). The NPs prepared with CD-PEG-PLGA-DOT/PD manifested less cytotoxicity respect to NPs prepared with HA-PEG-PLGA-DOT/PD. Furthermore, DOT/PD-loaded HA-PEG-PLGA and CD-PEG-PLGA NPs expressed significantly higher transfection in CD44 overexpressed U87 than in CD44-negative HepG2. The endocytosis of HA-PEG-PLGA-DOT/PD NPs has proven to be mainly dominated by micropinocytosis and the endocytosis of CD-PEG-PLGA-DOT/PD NPs has proven to be dominated by the endocytosis pathway (clathrin-mediated). The high selectivity to CD44 U87 cancer cells and low cytotoxicity in L929 normal cells made CD-PEG-PLGA NPs HA a promising nanocarriers for gene delivery.^[68]

α -tocopheryl succinate (TOS) was grafted on HA backbone to prepare NPs with improved cancer cell identification and simultaneous ability to overcome multidrug resistance. HA- α -TOS (HT) conjugate and D- α -tocopheryl polyethylene glycol succinate (TpgS) were used to prepare HHTTP NPs with docetaxel loaded in its hydrophobic core. Primarily α -TOS was aminated and then chemically conjugated with HA. The drug-loaded HHTTP NPs were obtained by an emulsification-solvent evaporation method. Briefly, HT conjugates were mixed with TpgS and dissolved in distilled water. Then, DTX was added in chloroform and sonicated in the ice bath by a probe ultrasonicator to prepare the emulsion and after evaporation, the NPs suspension was purified by means of a filter. The tumor cell recognition, cytotoxicity, and mitochondria-specific apoptotic pathways for the HHTTP NPs were observed in MCF/Adr cells (Pg overexpressing cancer model), indicating that the formulated composed of DTX/ α -TOS present in the HHTTP NP could synergistically bypass the acquisition and intrinsic multidrug resistance in MCF-7/Adr cells. In vivo tests on the MCF/Adr xenografted mice models showed a higher tumor tissue accumulation and exhibited markedly improved antiresistance tumor efficacy with lower toxicity of HHTTP NPs than blank NPs. The mechanisms of HHTTP NP to overcome multidrug resistance and improve antiresistance efficacy can be due to by CD44 receptor-targeted delivery and Pg efflux inhibition, and at the same time to increase antitumor efficacy by synergistic effect between DTX and anticancer agent of α -TOS killing tumor cells.^[69]

NPs for hepatocellular carcinoma (HC) dual-targeted stimuli responsive, able to supply a controlled release of doxorubicin (DOX) based on the reduction of cleavable HA glycyrrheticin-conjugate (HACG) have been developed. HA-Cyst-GA conjugate was obtained forming an amide bond between the carboxylic groups of HA and the amine group of GA-Cyst. To prepare the NPs the lyophilized HA-Cyst-GA was dissolved in distilled water. Subsequently, the solution underwent a sonication treatment,

using an ice bath to avoid heat buildup, followed by purification by filtration. In aqueous solution HACG conjugate aggregated to form NPs with a drug loading capacity of 33.9%. The cellular uptake tests showed higher affinity of the NPs to hepatoma cells (HepG2) compared to breast cancer cells (MDA-MB-231). The cytotoxic potency of HACG-DOX-NPs resulted increased over their nonresponsive free counterparts. In vivo studies demonstrated that HACG-DOX-NPs mediated both a faster intracellular release and nuclear delivery of DOX compared to the negative control. In vivo imaging study performed on H22 tumor-bearing mice showed that the NPs (DiR-labeled) an accumulation in the liver and hepatoma tissues, confirming their targeting abilities. All these findings confirmed that HACG-DOX-NPs is a promising DOX delivery carrier for hepatocellular carcinoma therapy.^[70]

3. Surface Functionalization with HA

3.1. HA-CD44 Active Biological Targeting: Role of Surface Functionalization

Active targeting based on recognition of specific molecular target is an effective modality to enhance drug selectivity and efficacy in cancer therapy. HA acts as a ligand for three main cell surface receptors: CD44 receptor, hyaluronate-mediated motility receptor (RHAMM) and intercellular adhesion molecule 1 (ICAM-1), which perform various functions.^[71] Among these, CD44, a transmembrane glycoprotein (molecular weight of 85–200 kDa), is the most largely distributed cell surface recognized receptor for HA binding.^[72,73] CD44 isoforms take part in various signaling pathways including morphogenesis, proliferation, and wound repair, and growing evidence suggests that CD44 receptors overexpression are involved in tumor progression and subsequently in the metastasis starting process.^[74] Indeed, concerning the drug delivery systems used for cancer therapy, the interaction between the HA-CD44 receptors has been largely used as an active tumor targeting. CD44 receptor-mediated endocytosis in cancer cells and the capability of the CD44 receptor in vivo to be a tumor target by HA-based nanodevices (**Figure 5**) were broadly identified in a wide set of cancer cells, such as breast cancer, glioblastoma, hepatoma, lung adenocarcinoma, and melanoma.^[75,76] Biologically, HA interacts with CD44 receptor within the HA-binding domain (HABD, often 25–174aa), a well-conserved domain across species, and reportedly requires a minimum of a 6-mer (hexasaccharide, or 3 HA repeat units) and optimally an 8-mer (octasaccharide, or 4 HA repeat units) for binding.^[77] Carboxylic acid and primary alcohol groups are even involved in the interactions among HA and the HA binding domain (HABD) of CD44, the carboxylic acid absorbs most of the negative charge of HA and is supposedly involved in interactions with at least two residues (Ala102, Ala103) of the HABD, whilst the primary alcohol is involved with at least one residue (Tyr109) of the HABD.^[19,78] Various mechanisms have been reported concerning the regulation of CD44 receptor-mediated HA binding. The first type is based on the changes in affinity between individual receptors and HA, exerted by changes in CD44 glycosylation. A second type refers to the repetitive structure (GlcNAc₁–4GlcUA)_nc of HA molecules, containing multiple CD44 binding sites, thus individual HA chains can interact on the cell surface simultaneously with many CD44 receptors. Furthermore, vari-

ations in the density and arrangement of CD44 on the cell surface, which also include local enrichment or clustering, can influence these multivalent interactions. Finally, the last mechanism is based on the changes in the conformational state of HA either by means of the formation of macromolecular protein complexes or differences in HA chain length that can influence both HA binding and its biological function.^[79]

3.2. Surface Modification of Inorganic Nanoparticles

Tumor microenvironment possesses more abnormalities than its surrounded tissues and cells. For instance, lower pH and overexpression of some biologically active molecules differentiate tumor cells from normal cells.^[71] Insight of this, different kinds of nanosized structures containing a wide set of cargo have been modified with biologically active molecules, e.g. HA, to improve the targeted delivery. In addition, to diminish the side effect to attain improved cancer therapy, targeted delivery using functionalized NPs have been exploited. These functionalized nanostructures can feel the tumor microenvironment, and subsequently discriminate, and target the cancer cells. Many successful studies have been performed using HA receptor-mediated endocytosis nanosystems, due to their features such as polyanionic and hydrophilicity, leading to low accumulation of NPs in cancer cells to liberate anticancer agents.^[80]

HA was applied as a targeting ligand to create HA-functionalized metal-based NPs, e.g. bismuth oxide NPs (HA-Bi₂O₃ NPs), as a multifunctional theranostic platform. The aim of the tumor-targeted probe is to afford spatial- and temporal-specific computed tomography (CT) as well as to enable cancer radioresistance. The existence of such hydrophilic functional groups on the surface of HA-Bi₂O₃ NPs ameliorates the dispersibility of these NPs in aqueous solutions. The outcome exhibited very low cytotoxicity in all tested concentrations. Also, the hemocompatibility of HA-Bi₂O₃ NPs was assessed in vitro, by applying hemolysis assay. The presented data confirm the high potentiality of HA-Bi₂O₃ NPs to use as theranostic agents for CT imaging-guided radiotherapy in the diagnosis and treatment of tumors.^[81]

Chemotherapy is a mostly applied therapeutic modality for cancer therapy. Nevertheless, some negative factors such as systemic toxicity multidrug resistance, and bioavailability during the therapy, obliged researchers to investigate other possible treatments with better features.^[82] In order to reduce the collateral effects of chemotherapy drugs (e.g., doxorubicin), a wide variety of nanocarriers, i.e., graphene oxide,^[83] and mesoporous silica^[84] have been exploited for delivery of such therapeutics. In light of this, hydroxyapatite (HAP) is also presented as a nanoparticle-based nanocarrier (**Figure 6**). This nanoparticle was combined with polyethyleneimine (PEI) for coating onto the surface of HAP for extra stabilization and as a linker for further modifications with HA, as an efficient targeting agent was engineered in this nanoparticle. The preparation and fabrication of the nanodevice with specific targeting ability were conducted successfully. The results indicated that the NPs possess higher dispersibility and stability in water than the pristine unmodified HAP particles. Besides, the functionalized NPs showed a pH-responsive release profile which is in favor of cancer cells, having lower pH than

Figure 5. Tumor target by HA-based nanocarriers, CD44 receptor-mediated endocytosis. CD44 receptor in detail shows three domains: extracellular, transmembrane and a cytoplasmic domain. The extracellular region of CD44s is composed of two regions: the highly conserved constant region, presumed domain responsible for the binding of the HA (HABD), and the region closest to the membrane, named variant region, in which alternative splicing enables the insertion of extra aa sequence from different exons of the CD44 gene. Moreover, the extracellular domain also contains six cysteine residues, that most likely form three disulfide bonds, and sites for five-conserved *N*-glycosylation located in the amino-terminal 120 aa of CD44.

the surrounding tissues. This was confirmed by evaluating the therapeutic efficiency of the designed nanocarrier, as the NPs significantly enhanced the effective targeted delivery of doxorubicin.^[85]

Other sorts of treatments such as photothermal therapy with nanoplatforms have been exploited. In particular, mesoporous silica NPs for synergistic targeted chemo-photothermal therapy were designed and constructed. To further improve the efficiency of these NPs, the external surfaces of polydopamine functionalized-nanosilica have been decorated by HA. The nanodevice showed both high biocompatibility and drug loading capacity, and high photothermal performance once irradiated in near-infrared light (NIR). The outcome of in vitro drug release

experiment exhibited that drug release is pH dependent and NIR laser irradiation.^[86]

Gold nanorods are another type of materials that were extensively exploited both for synergetic photothermal chemotherapy of breast cancer and for active targeting delivery.^[87,88] In a study, gold nanorods were functionalized with HA to have NPs with pH- and light-responsivity. It can chemically load and carry anticancer drugs, such as doxorubicin, by a pH-sensitive hydrazone linkage. As these surface-modified NPs are negatively charged, they displayed enhanced stability in serum medium. Furthermore, the nanoplatform showed NIR irradiation and pH dual-responsive drug release with a high biocompatibility. According to the results, these NPs have both very good

Figure 6. A) Schematic illustration of polymeric NPs and application in cancer therapy. B) TEM image of the polymeric NPs. C) Schematic illustration of the procedure used to evaluate the phototherapeutic effect of polymeric NPs towards 3D MCF-7 spheroids. Reprinted with permission.^[93] Copyright 2019, Elsevier.

tumor-specific accumulation and a long blood circulation time. The *in vivo* experiments of the photothermal chemotherapy treatments evidenced that the tumor was entirely removed without serious collateral effects^[89] (Table 1).

3.3. Surface Modification of Organic Nanoparticles

Apart from inorganic NPs, organic-based nanostructures have been fabricated or functionalized with HA.^[90,91] There are different strategies including physical and chemical methods used to coat polymeric particles with HA. Chemical modifications can occur on two available functional groups, such as carboxylic and hydroxyl acid groups, on the backbone of the HA chain.^[92]

Organic NPs with HA covalently bonded to the surface were prepared with the nanoprecipitation method by using a HA copolymer with the hydrolyzed poly(maleic anhydride-alt-1-octadecene) (PMAO). NPs obtained were loaded with a formulation of IR78 and DOX, to prepare a device that combines photothermal therapy and chemotherapy. *In vitro* experiments on NHDF and MCF-7 cells illustrated how loaded NPs did not alter the viability of the cells after 48 h, and a selective internalization in MCF-7 cells. Meaningful reductions in tumor cells were observed only under irradiation with NIR light for the NPs loaded with IR78 (59%) and IR78-DOX formulations (66%). These results illustrated the on-demand anticancer activity of the prepared devices, and the synergy effect of the IR78-DOX respect to the dye alone. Interestingly, the encapsulation process could

increase the absorption peak of IR780 to 808 nm by more than twofold, which elevates its photothermal ability and cytocompatibility (Figure 6).^[93]

One of the most promising delivery materials is biodegradable poly(lactide-*co*-glycolide) acid (PLGA). For physical methods, amphiphilic materials such as pluronic (poloxamers) have been employed as lipophilic molecules between PLGA core and HA shell (Figure 7) (Table 1).^[94] The fabrication of HA-coated NPs do not involve a chemical reaction and the self-assembly mechanism is driven from oppositely electrostatically charged of the HA and another polymer. This strategy allows for maintaining the HA structure unchanged. Indeed, in HA/PLGA NPs formulations, HA constitutes a hydrophilic shell while the PLGA represents the hydrophobic core. The HA/PLGA NPs are the most used in the tumor-targeting toward CD44-overexpressing cell lines. HA/PLGA NPs (IRIN)-loaded for the release of the anticancer drug for breast carcinoma have been developed. PLGA is placed inside while HA is placed outside of the NPs, with amphiphilic poloxamers (F127 and F68) acting as a link between PLGA and HA. Irinotecan-loaded NPs were fabricated by a single emulsion with solvent evaporation technique. The HA/PLGA NPs (IRIN)-loaded *in vitro* results showed an Irinotecan release up to 12 days. Furthermore, the cytotoxicity assay demonstrated that HA/PLGA NPs can deliver more than one drug into cancer cells leading in a higher killing effect on CD44-overexpressing cells, likely due to the functionalization of the NPs with HA.^[94]

HA-decorated cationic lipid-PLGA hybrid NPswere developed specifically for the cytosolic delivery of genes for

Figure 7. A) Schematic representation of NP preparation single emulsion–solvent evaporation technique. B) Selected TEM micrographs of functionalized NPs. B) Reprinted with permission.^[94] Copyright 2016, Elsevier.

immunotherapy.^[95] Cationic lipid composed of 1,2-dioleoyl-3-trimethyl ammonium-propane have been extensively studied due to their ease formation of nanocomplexes with anionic peptides and plasmid DNA encoding for antigens able to induce immune responses in vivo. However, high concentrations of the positive charges can determine high cytotoxicity, negatively affecting immune response. To bypass this limitation HA can be used as layer of anionic polymer to coat by electrostatic interaction these particles, for shielding positive charge and producing a stable delivery system. Dendritic cells (DCs) can bind these NPs, which leads to induction of specific antigen, CD4+, and T-cell responses, CD8+, simplification of antigen specific IgG antibody production, secretion of cytokines. The results exhibited that cell biocompatibility could be improved with an HA-based coating.^[95]

4. Cancer Therapy

4.1. Current Therapeutic Approaches

Lately, targeted antineoplastic drugs, oligonucleotide therapeutics delivery, and immunotherapy have been tested as strategies in cancer translational and clinical research. Among nanomaterials, HA-based nanodevices have been demonstrated effective in many cancer treatments. HA performance as ligand to promote active targeting, used in several nanodevices, has been shown in different research works. Encouraging results in vitro and in vivo, against melanoma,^[96] breast cancer,^[97] and pulmonary adenocarcinoma cells,^[98] as to aid intravitreal drug administration and delivery for gene therapy in retinal site^[99] and to decrease the im-

munogenicity due to protein corona,^[100] have demonstrated HA capability to boost antitumor action.

4.1.1. Antineoplastic Drug Conjugated Polymers

The most studied approach in recent years is certainly the possibility of using HA-based nanodevices for the delivery of chemotherapeutic agents. HA only or in mixture with conventional chemotherapeutics (i.e., doxorubicin, taxol, methotrexate, vincristine, imatinib, gemcitabine, cisplatin, 5-fluorouracil, etc.) seems to be good new opportunity in antineoplastic therapy. Indeed, antineoplastic drugs conjugated, entrapped or encapsulated within HA-based nanodevices can lead improvement in their solubility and dispersibility in aqueous media decreasing their side effects. Polymer drug conjugates production was proposed for the transport of tiny hydrophobic therapeutic molecules to their specific sites of action.^[101] These drug delivery systems are essentially composed of a water soluble polymer, in which drug molecules is covalently bound. As already reported in the literature, some of these approaches, such as the increase of the water solubility of low soluble or insoluble drugs, preserve the activities of the drugs during circulation in the body and allow the specific target to the site of action.^[102] One of the best candidates to design prodrugs is HA, indeed due to its physicochemical properties can act both as a hydrophilic carrier and as a CD44 ligand for active targeting.^[103] As already reported in the literature from the “washing line model” the polymer drug conjugates do not occur in solution, since in water solution the conjugates form micelles, nanoaggregates, or gels, with the drug

developing a core/shell (drug/HA) structures.^[53] To increase the therapeutic effect of HA-based conjugates,^[98] chemical synthesis must be consider different pivotal features, such as the stability in vivo of conjugate and the efficient release of the active moiety to target cell.

Paclitaxel (PTX) has been extensively used in breast, bladder, lung, melanoma, and ovarian cancers,^[104] due to its low aqueous solubility pharmaceutical excipients are required for its application.^[105] To overcome these problems, several chemical strategies have been used to conjugate PTX to polymers. The most frequent chemical modification used for polymeric drug conjugates is C2 based, due to its ease in releasing PTX from conjugates. Nevertheless, high drug loading covered the receptor element recognized from HA. The carboxyl can influence biological function of HA, water solubility and the drug loading of HA-based conjugates. Moreover, the contact between HA and CD44 receptors is determined by hydrogen bonding and for this reason, the carboxyl group of GlcA plays an important role in recognition of the receptor. In the case of HA 6 PTX, the conjugation of PTX occurred to the C6 position of HA, overcoming the aforementioned limitations. The C6 primary hydroxyl group of HA was chemically modified and then conjugated with PTX through an amide linkage without hampering the biological HA functions. HA 6 PTX has been showed higher cytotoxicity rate and enhanced apoptosis against HepG2 and A549 cells due to the increased cellular uptake of the drug mediated by HA mediated endocytosis receptor compared free PTX^[106] (Table 1).

Doxorubicin (DOX) is one of the most effective chemotherapeutics used in cancer treatments, even if its use is limited by its hepatic, renal, and cardiac toxicity.^[107] To overcome these limitations new DOX formulations have been designed, HA drug conjugates with both DOX and gemcitabine (GEM) to control the release kinetics of each drug have been fabricated. It was shown that polymer conjugates release GEM earlier than DOX, resulting more effective in cytotoxicity of breast cancer cells. Furthermore, the combination of dual drug conjugate more effectively prevents the growth of orthotopic 4T1 tumor model in vivo, both intravenous and nonlocal subcutaneous injections, compared to free DOX and GEM and the HA conjugates with each drug. In this work has been highlighted both the importance of the use of HA as a drug delivery platform for different cancer types and the importance to understand the release rates of the synergistic drug carriers^[108] (Table 1).

HA-4-carboxybenzaldehyde-DOX (HA-CBA-DOX) prodrug conjugates have been fabricated; this novel macromolecule can target CD44-overexpressed tumor cells and release DOX, that is passively triggered by the acidic microenvironment of tumor cells. Drug release in vitro tests have been demonstrated that the polymeric HA-CBA-DOX were pH-responsive and showed quicker drug release at pH = 5.0 than at pH = 7.0. Moreover, cytotoxicity experiment showed that the HA-CBA-DOX displayed high inhibition toward HeLa cells proliferation. Therefore, the HA-based structure designed in this study can maintain the long time circulation in the whole body, elude tumor infiltration, avoid clearance by the reticuloendothelial system, transport the drug into the target sites, and more importantly release the drug directly into the site of action.^[109]

HA coupled NPs bearing 5 fluorouracil (5FU) encapsulated in enteric coated pellets to release the drug in the colon have been

investigated. The realize profile of 5FU in vitro mimicked the transit from the stomach to the colon indicated that 5FU was protected against expulsion in the stomach and small intestine. Moreover, the high local concentration of drugs would be able to increase the exposure time and thus, could enhance antitumor efficacy, decreasing the systemic toxicity in the treatment of colon cancer.^[110]

HA conjugated with cisplatin was developed via the linkage between cisplatin and carboxyl groups of HA using silver nitrate as an activating agent. Then, HA cisplatin conjugate exhibited enhanced antitumor efficacies and reduced toxicities against several types of cancers, such as non-small cell lung cancer, head and neck squamous cell carcinoma and ovarian cancer.^[111] In particular, HA cisplatin conjugates has been investigated for lung cancer treatment. The new formulation conjugates effectively decrease the cell proliferation both in bi dimensional and three dimensional cell cultures. More interestingly, in vivo test have showed the efficacy of this polymeric cisplatin delivery platform, via intratracheal administration in mice, using an aerosol spray into lung tumor site. The efficacious of this platform against lung cancer have resulted in 90% decrease of tumor nodule numbers compared to PBS control groups^[112] (Table 1).

Camptothecin (CPT) inhibits topoisomerase I enzyme in DNA. This compound is slightly aqueous soluble, its solubility may increase due to the opening of the lactone ring which generates the water-soluble CPT carboxylate, but this drastically decreases cellular uptake. To increase both its stability and solubility, CPT based drugs have been developed, which are now used in anticancer chemotherapy. HA-CPT conjugate has been synthesized, composed of disulfide-linked to the carboxylic group, which are responsive to high level of intracellular glutathione (GSH) in cancer cells. Thanks to its amphiphilic property, the HA-CPT conjugate is able to form micellar structure in water solution with physicochemical properties depending on the degree of substitution on HA backbone. In the breast carcinoma cells model in mouse, this system exhibited higher tumor suppression and inhibition of lung metastasis than free CPT group.^[113]

A hydrophobic cytotoxic drug, the hydrogenated nimesulide (*N*-[4-amino-2-phenoxyphenyl] methanesulfonamide) has been conjugated, through a carbodiimide coupling reaction, to HA with high molecular weight (MW) 360 kDa and low MW HA (HA 43 kDa) respectively. In vivo test showed that both high and low MW HA could be selectively accumulated in CD44 overexpressing HT 29 colorectal tumor cells. Furthermore, for both HA conjugated systems a rapid tumor shrinkage and successfully inhibition of tumor proliferation, of about 82.3% and 76.4%, respectively, after 24 days have been evaluated in this model.^[114]

4-Phenylbutyric acid (PbA) installed HA-based NPs to increase anticancer potentials of curcumin have been developed for lung cancer therapy. PbA acts as histone deacetylase inhibitor, after the HA conjugation, both in vitro and in vivo, have been exhibited a decrement of tumor cell growth and increase of apoptosis. Curcumin loaded HAPbA NPs have been displayed significantly lower IC50 value then curcumin and HAPbA. In vivo tests showed an efficient tumor growth arrest and apoptosis in lung tumor due to these systems, coupling CD44 receptor targeting and histone deacetylase inhibition of HAPbA NPs, and increasing the effect of curcumin.^[115]

Figure 8. Schematic illustration of HA-based polymeric conjugate grafted with PEG through MMP9 cleavable linker. Since this conjugate had a PEG corona detachable in the presence of MMP9, the HA of the conjugate could be exposed only at the site of tumor, shortening its cellular uptake mediated by endocytosis mechanism. Therefore, cancer cells may present antigenic epitopes on the MHC class I molecules, letting the immunological rejection by cytotoxic T lymphocytes CTLs. Reprinted with permission.^[120] Copyright 2017, Elsevier.

4.1.2. Cancer Immunotherapy

Immunotherapy has become in cancer treatment area a valid therapeutic option.^[116] Immunostimulatory effect, currently explored in cancer immunotherapy, includes the immune system stimulation acting by specific antigens and immunostimulatory molecules, as cytokines or interferons.^[117] HA nanodevice in cancer immunotherapy represents lately a promising tool. Indeed, HA, because of its intrinsic anti-inflammatory and anti-immunogenic properties, has the ability to regulate the immune modulation.^[118] Furthermore, interesting study concerning the modulation (activation and reprogramming) of macrophages on the basis of the different HA MW has been conducted. Low MW HA induced a classical activated conformation, established by the upregulation of pro inflammatory genes, such as TNF, CD80, IL12b and nos2 an increased secretion of nitric oxide and TNF α . High MW HA endorsed an alternatively activated conformation, by the regulation of pro resolution gene transcription, as mrc1, arg1, and IL10, and increased arginase activity. This awareness can be used to aid the design of biomaterials based on HA to make the best use of the natural biological response to HA.^[119]

Polymeric conjugates have been developed with responsiveness ability to matrix metalloproteinase 9 (MMP9), made up of PEGylated HA, that acts as targeting moiety, and of ovalbumin (OVA), as foreign antigen (**Figure 8**). The MMP9-cleavable linker has been inserted between PEG and the HA backbone to simplify the detachment of the PEG corona from the conjugate at the tumor site. Results have demonstrated that these systems have been effectively taken up by the CD44 over expressing TC1 can-

cer cells in the presence of MMP9 via receptor mediated endocytosis and that the tumor growth was significantly withdrawn, due to antigen presentation on the tumor cells.^[120]

The combination effect of IFN α incorporated HA Tyr hydrogels plus sorafenib in a mouse model for the management of metastatic renal cell carcinoma have been studied. The results have been suggested that HA Tyr hydrogels efficiently inhibited tumor growth in nude mice model of human renal carcinoma xenografts, and furthermore the drug delivery system extended the biological half-life of natural human IFN α and enhanced its anticancer effects on human renal cells carcinoma^[121] (Table 1).

Two HA combination vaccine adjuvants including hydrophobic monophosphoryl lipid, QS21, and imiquimod, R837, named HMQ and HMR respectively have been developed. HA-based combination vaccine adjuvants concurred to enhance both humoral and cellular immunity, fundamental for efficient cancer immunotherapy. The results have demonstrated the immunostimulatory effects of HMQ and HMR and the inhibition of tumor proliferation in mice model of lymphoma expressing OVA^[122] (Table 1).

4.1.3. Oligonucleotide Therapeutics

Oligonucleotide therapeutics, such as antisense oligonucleotides, siRNA and miRNA, have been shown enormous potential, increasing interest in the design of nanocarriers designed to encourage the overcoming of critical biological barriers and achieving their goal in the tissues^[123] Oligonucleotide

necessitates chemical modifications and nanosized carriers to avoid stability problems *in vivo*. The HA-based nanodevices may be used in oligonucleotide delivery systems for management of CD44 over expressing cancers. Indeed, HA can be used successfully to modify the surface of cationic complexes, by trapping the material in a polymeric/lipid matrix, and to decorate the surface of nanocarriers loaded with polynucleotides.^[124]

Active targeted HA recoated *N,N,N*-trimethyl chitosan (TMC) NPs have been generated to transport IL 6 and STAT3 specific small interfering RNAs (siRNAs) to cancer cells over expressing CD44. The HA and CD44 interaction increases the specificity and efficacy of cellular uptake of the NPs. The results have been demonstrated that siRNA loaded NPs significantly inhibited the IL6 and STAT3 expression, associated with the arrest of proliferation, colony formation, migration, and angiogenesis in cancer cells. HA-TMC NPs have resulted in a powerful vector in gene therapy and their application for the silencing of IL 6 and STAT3^[125] (Table 1).

Interestingly albumin sericin NPs (AlbSer NPs) as a novel siRNA delivery system for laryngeal cancer treatment have been developed. NPs have been modified with poly-L-lysine (PLL) for siRNA binding and decorated with HA to target laryngeal cancer cell line. HA-PLL-siRNA/Alb-Ser (2:1) NP-mediated gene silencing resulted in a significant inhibition of cell growth and induction of apoptosis in cells.^[126]

Chitosan NPs modified with HA loaded with cyanine 3 (Cy3) labeled siRNA (sCS NPs HA) have been prepared and characterized for targeted therapy in non-small cell lung cancer. *In vitro* results showed that CS NPs HA of small size, as 100 and 200 nm, were not cytotoxic and successfully carried the Cy3 labeled siRNA into A549 cells via CD44 receptor, inhibiting the proliferation of the cells by downregulation of the BCL2 gene. *In vivo* test findings showed that sCS NPs HA carried greater amounts of Cy3 labeled siRNA into tumor site, diminishing tumor growth, compared to unmodified, without HA, NPs loaded with siRNA (sCS NPs) and to nude Cy3-labeled siRNA^[127] (Table 1).

4.1.4. Combination of Therapeutic Approaches

Combination therapy aims to improve the possibility of a therapeutic approach based on the simultaneous combination of multiple therapeutic methodologies for the cancer therapy. This would favor the generation of synergistic anticancer actions, multiple drugs, immunotherapeutic and/or gene therapeutic agent delivery can suppress the chemoresistance that causes the major risk of failure and increase at the same time the killing effects on cancer cells.^[128] HA-based nanodevices have shown great potential in combination therapy thanks to the intrinsic properties of HA to have different functional parts that replace and therefore the possibility of conjugating more than one therapeutic agent.

HA containing lipid NPs co-loaded with cisplatin (CDDP) and sorafenib (SRF) for the treatment of gastric cancer have been investigated and HA and CDDP including lipid prodrug was synthesized using polyethylene glycol (PEG) as a linker (HA-PEG-CDDP). HA-PEG-CDDP and SRF were enclosed into the lipid NPs by nanoprecipitation method. *In vivo* testing including bio distribution and accumulation in tumor tissue indicated that the

HA-based nanodevices enhanced the antitumor effect of drugs and reduced the systemic toxicity effects.^[129]

HA modified irinotecan and gene co loaded lipid polymer hybrid nanocarriers (HA I/D LPNs) for targeted colorectal cancer combination therapy have been developed. The *in vitro* and *in vivo* gene transfection and antitumor ability of the nanodevice has been investigated on colorectal cancer cells and mice bearing colorectal cancer model. The outcomes have revealed the maximum tumor growth inhibition effectiveness and the greatest conspicuous transfection efficiency *in vivo* using these nanocarriers^[130] (Table 1).

Hybrid mesoporous silica nanoparticle (HMSN), molecularly both organic and inorganic, coated with HA and polyethyleneimine (PEI) has been generated for the gene chemotherapeutic therapy of breast cancer. HMSN with tumor sensitive disulfide bond and able to target receptors ligated by HA can be degraded when it encounters high concentration of glutathione (GSH) and hyaluronidase (HAase). This approach smartly merges biodegradability and biological function resulting in the synergistic antitumor activity of gene and chemical drug on breast cancer.^[131]

The Lys Leu Val Phe Phe (KLVFF) peptide motifs targeted by HA functionalized liposomes to the tumor have been developed. The strategy involves spontaneous *in situ* self-assembly to form nanofibers with a net like structure covering around tumor cells, thus limiting direct contact between tumor cells and TME. The nanofibril coatings on tumor cells significantly inhibited tumor cells induced platelet aggregation *in vitro* and prevent the adhesion of platelet around circulating tumor cells (CTCs) *in vivo*, thus limit the pro-metastasis effect of platelets and prevent the early metastasis. Results in 4T1 breast cancer mice model have shown that the nanonets stably retain in the primary tumor site for over 72 h and effectively prevent the activation of intratumoral platelet, which suppress tumor progression and spontaneous lung metastasis^[132] (Table 1).

4.2. HA As an Excipient for Anticancer Drugs

Recently, the HA has been used as an excipient to specific ionic formulations able to incorporate different anticancer drugs such as doxorubicin, irinotecan, tamoxifen, 5 fluorouracil 5FU, methotrexate MTX, into the HA network, using an approach named HyACT technology (Alchemia Ltd.).^[133] The main advantage, from the regulatory point of view, of these formulations, is based on the absence of any chemical modifications or conjugation either HA with the drug.

New polymeric HA-based excipients have been developed, composed of papain grating S-protected HA/lithocholic acid block copolymer (PAP-HA-ss-LCA), tamoxifen (TMX) loaded, as an amphiphilic mucus penetrating stabilizer for targeting breast cancer epithelial cells overexpressed CD44 receptors. *In vitro* study demonstrated release kinetics indicated 80% release within 48 h; furthermore, the cytotoxicity studies showed that TMX-pap-HA-ss-LCA could efficiently kill MCF 7 breast cancer cells as compared to the pure TMX drug. *In vivo* studies showed a permeation study displayed sevenfold higher permeation of TMX by TMX-pap-HA-ss-LCA in contrast to pure TMX.^[134]

Concerning preclinical and/or clinical trials HA was used as an excipient in a formulation with irinotecan for the management of metastatic colorectal carcinoma. Phase I and II clinical studies showed that the HA-irinotecan formulation was safe, well-tolerated and that the therapeutic efficacy of irinotecan was increased with the use of HA as an excipient.^[133] Unfortunately, the Phase III clinical study did not show significant results in terms of improving progression-free survival. One option could be based on the enhancement of the activity of the HA conjugates, to overcome tumor multidrug resistance, by co-loading or linking more powerful anticancer agents. Multiple anticancer drugs (e.g., irinotecan, doxorubicine, 5-FU, and MTX) have been investigated in clinical trials by utilizing HA as a targeting moiety.^[135] Concerning 5-FU and HA-irinotecan in combination with cetuximab, a Phase II trial was initiated (NCT02216487) by Alchemia Oncology. This trial aims to investigate the use of HA-Irinotecan in a single-arm trial of FOLF(HA) in combination with cetuximab in patients with KRAS wild-type metastatic colorectal cancer. Also, these studies aim to confirm the safety and efficacy of FOLF(HA) in combination with cetuximab as second-line therapy in patients with metastatic colon rectal cancer.

5. Conclusion and Future Perspective

HA has proven to be a molecule suitable for drug delivery application and able to overcome the limits of the administration of conventional antineoplastic drugs, thanks to its ability to reach the CD44 receptor overexpressed in numerous tumors. As reported in the literature, devices based on HA nanomaterials such as hydrogels and NPs proved to be the most advanced technologies in preclinical tests.^[136] A wide set of methods are described in the literature for the production of HA-based vehicles, whose properties can be improved and modulated by combining HA with other components, and/or changing the condition of reaction. Since cancer cells exhibit different environmental conditions with respect to healthy cells, researchers directed their attention to the design of stimuli-responsive carriers (e.g., hydrogels and nanodevices) aiming to improve the targeting ability and enhance the anticancer activity. For this reason, the use of nanodevices in combination with methods for the controlled modification of the tumor microenvironments should be considered as a fundamental parameter to develop promising strategy for the advance of nanomedicine for cancer therapy.^[137] The examples reported in this review highlight the deep scientific interest on HA-based hydrogels for the cancer therapy. Even so, at current time no hydrogel-based devices obtained from natural polymers results approved from FDA for this kind of application.^[138] One of the difficulties in the passage of hydrogels from laboratory tests to preclinical trials lies with the nonspecificity of subcutaneous ectopic tumor models, that are the most employed in *in vivo* studies.^[139] According to literature, the development of more specific protocols by using orthotopic tumor models could provide more accurate information on the evolution of the tumor in presence of the devices, and encourage subsequent development.

Nowadays, much interest is extending to encourage advances in HA acid-based nanodevices for cancer therapies, including therapies based on the delivery of antineoplastic drugs, immunotherapies, oligonucleotide therapeutics and the most

promising “Combination therapies.” HA ability to target receptors that are overexpressed in cancer cells (i.e., CD44) is a tremendous advantage, and it represents the preferential strategy in cancer therapy, but in the meantime HA maintains also the ability to bind specific receptors in healthy cells. Thus, the foremost challenge is to find strategies to increase the binding affinity of HA only to tumor cells receptors. Furthermore, carefully directed studies have been demonstrated pro-inflammatory functions of low-MW HA and its capability to promote the activation of macrophage (polarization).^[119] Although HA is commonly considered nontoxic and biocompatible this aspect should be more elucidated to allow for a well understanding of the potential of HA-based (nano) devices in cancer immunotherapy. Moreover, another important challenge would be to investigate the mechanisms of molecular interaction and internalization of these nanodevices. In fact, to date, this aspect remains little explored, and it is difficult to standardize the mechanism of action and interaction of these nanosystems in the cells. It is not yet clear how the size of the HA fragment affects receptor activation, and how different effects can be influenced by different receptor clusters with which HA interacts. Furthermore, among the HA-based (nano) devices must considered clearly the molecular weight of HA, the protocol of crosslinking for receptor binding, the degradation and the fragmentation products to ensure suitability for the final application, promote an anti-inflammatory response and to moderate side effects.^[140]

Unfortunately, the escalating complexity in the synthetic process of many devices proposed in literature and the obtaining of Chemistry, Manufacturing and Controls (CMC) and Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) requirements is also an obstacle for the translation from preclinical to clinical application and succeeding commercialization. Precisely for this limit, scientists should readily consider nanomedicine scale-up as critical aspect already during early nanodevices design and engineering.^[141]

Among the drug delivery technologies polymer-drug conjugates and injectable formulations represent the most recent. However, the main obstacle for HA conjugates for their efficacy in cancer therapy is because of their classification as new chemical entities; therefore, physical-chemical characterizations, such as the drug release patterns, drug loading, particle size, and morphology, must be carefully optimized.^[142] Most of the clinical data have shown a remarkable reduction of adverse effects, but their efficacy still needs to be improved significantly.

Overall, the data here collected make a strong case for the continuation of research into the use of HA-based (Nano) devices for future clinical cancer therapy.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Keywords

cancer therapy, cell internalization, functionalization, hyaluronic acid, surface modifications

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